

COMPUTER-ASSISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING: ITS EFFECTIVENESS IN ENHANCING RECEPTIVE SKILLS OF COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Computer-Assisted Language Learning: Its Effectiveness in Enhancing Receptive Skills of College Students

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Abstract

Listening and reading are receptive skills that are crucial components of language learning. This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of Computer-Assisted Language Learning software in enhancing the receptive skills of college students during the Academic Year 2022-2023. This study is anchored on the theory of constructivism and Input Processing Theory. The study utilized a descriptive research design. The study participants were two hundred twenty-nine (299) first-year college students of a private tertiary school in Bacolod City. The pre-test and post-test scores of the college students in a standardized language test were used to determine the effectiveness of CALL. The results show that, generally, there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the students in terms of their listening and reading skills. The findings of this study suggest that students' receptive skills, may have improved as a result of incorporating CALL (Computer-Assisted Language Learning) into their English classes. Hence, it is recommended that CALL be used to develop students' receptive skills.

Keywords: *receptive skills, listening, reading, computer-assisted language learning*

Introduction

Language learning is an important aspect of modern education. The ability to communicate effectively in multiple languages has become increasingly important in today's globalized world. Receptive language skills, including listening and reading, are crucial components of language learning, as they allow individuals to understand and comprehend spoken and written language. However, students often face difficulties in acquiring receptive skills, such as listening and reading receptive, which hinder their overall language proficiency (Shamsudin et al., 2018). The traditional approach to language learning involves a teacher-centered approach, where the instructor imparts knowledge, and the students are passive recipients. However, this approach is gradually losing ground due to its inability to engage students effectively and efficiently.

One potential solution to this challenge is the use of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) strategies. CALL has been described as a "promising approach to language learning" that offers "multifaceted opportunities to learn" (Stockwell, 2017). With the rapid advancement of technology, computer-assisted language learning (CALL) has emerged as a popular and effective method for enhancing language skills. Moreover, Computer-Assisted Language Learning, refers to the use of computer technology to facilitate language learning through interactive multimedia materials, online resources, and language learning software, offering a range of benefits such as increased engagement, immediate feedback, and personalized learning experiences (González-Lloret & Ortega, 2014; Lee & Huang, 2018). CALL has been shown to be an effective tool for improving various aspects of language proficiency, including receptive skills (Plass, Chun, Mayer, & Leutner, 1998; Warschauer & Healey, 1998). A study conducted by Khoshsima and Mozakka (2017) on the effect of computer-assisted language learning on Iranian upper-intermediate EFL learners' listening skills, the results indicated that application of CALL do have a significant effect on improvement of learners' listening skills. However, no studies have been found out in determining the effectiveness of CALL in Bacolod City.

Also, the research focusing on the framework of understanding Jean Piaget's constructivism which is crucial for educators because it shows how each student's unique experiences and prior knowledge shape their learning. When it comes to language learning, using Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) can bring constructivism to life by allowing students to build their language skills through hands-on interaction and exploration. CALL tools, like multimedia resources and opportunities to communicate with native speakers online, give students real-world language experiences that make learning more meaningful. In line with Input Processing Theory which is one of the frameworks, CALL also tailors the difficulty of language input to just above the learner's current level, helping them make sense of new concepts without feeling overwhelmed.

Furthermore, the investigation was prompted by the challenges encountered by college students in comprehending both written and spoken language students who exhibit a tendency to peruse reading materials without comprehension and engage in listening activities without effectively applying comprehension skills and just being a passive recipient of all the lessons presented, thereby necessitating a study into their receptive skills. Also, this study aims to assess the effectiveness of the Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) program in enhancing the receptive skills of college students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of using Computer-Assisted Language Learning software in enhancing the receptive skills of college during the Academic Year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of receptive skills of college students before using Computer-Assisted Language Learning?
2. What is the level of receptive skills of college students after using Computer-Assisted Language Learning?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of receptive skills before and after using Computer-Assisted Language Learning?

Methodology

The methods presents the research design, research participants, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study determined the effectiveness of using Computer-Assisted Language Learning to the receptive skills of students. The study utilized a descriptive research design which seeks to describe and discover the improvement of the one-group pretest-posttest to determine the effectiveness of CALL in enhancing the receptive skills of college students. The pretest was done at the beginning of the second semester, Academic Year 2022-2023 and the post-test was administered at the end of the said semester. These tests were part of the students' curriculum for their English subject. The researcher made use of the data available in an English language learning software used in CALL. The results of pre-test and post-test were obtained from the platform as the data has been saved despite the students finishing this subject.

Participants

The participants of this study were the first-year college students of a private tertiary school in Bacolod City who were enrolled in the Second Semester, Academic Year 2022-2023. With a population of 1328 First-Year students, a significance level of 5% and a confidence level of 95%, using Cochran's formula, the sample size is 299. These 299 students were the participants of the study - 6 BS Business Administration, 2 BS Entrepreneurship, 32 BS Med Tech, 180 BS Nursing, 20 BS Pharmacy, 17 BS Physical Therapy, 18 BS Psychology, and 24 BS RadTech students. The participants were chosen using a stratified random sampling technique.

Instruments

The researcher utilized Dynamic English (1987) Standardized English Test officially purchased by the institution. This instrument is a standardized language test that has guidelines for score interpretation. Additionally, it is a comprehensive language learning platform designed to enhance language acquisition and proficiency through technology. The tests measure the listening and reading skills of the students. A multiple-choice type of test was used. They answered the test questions using a computer in the Computer Laboratory room. The same set of tests were given for the post-test. The pretest was administered at the beginning of the second semester, academic year 2022-2023, and the post-test was conducted at the end of that semester.

Data Procedure

Before conducting the study, the researcher sought permission from the higher authority, particularly from the Head of the College and the Dean, through a formal letter explaining the rationale and purpose of the study and the need for the data from the CALL. Additionally, the researcher ensured the necessary permission to utilize the CALL software. A letter was sent to the Office of the Registrar as well asking for the total number and list of first-year students from different courses during the second Semester of the Academic Year 2022-2023. The statistician computed for the sample size.

Then, during the conduct of the study, the researcher scheduled a meeting with the First Year students for orientation regarding the study and the Informed Consent Form. Lastly, the participants were asked to sign the Informed Consent Form. After obtaining the Informed Consent from the participants, the pre-test was administered. Additionally, a pre-test was conducted before the implementation of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) program, scheduled for the first week of the midterm class, to assess the initial proficiency level. The midterm lasted for 7 weeks, and the same duration applied to the endterm. Also, throughout the midterm and endterm classes, CALL was integrated, encompassing all relevant topics, with sessions lasting approximately 25-30 minutes. Following the semester's conclusion, a post-test was administered to evaluate progress.

After the study was conducted, the scores of the students were taken from the computer laboratory and from the CALL's manager. It was tallied, computed, and analyzed.

Statistical Treatment

Data was analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to achieve the study's objectives. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Microsoft Excel were utilized to process the data.

For problem number 1 and 2, the researcher used the mean and standard deviation to determine the respondents' receptive skills level before and after using Computer-Assisted Language Learning.

For problem 3, the researcher used the paired sample t-test to determine the significant difference in the level of receptive skills before and after using Computer-Assisted Language.

The table below is the basis of the verbal interpretation of the level of receptive skills of the participants.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher acknowledged the participants' privacy, maintaining the confidentiality of data as well as using the information gained for research purposes only to ensure the ethical soundness of the study. Before the conduct of the study, an Informed Consent Form was obtained from the participants. Since, the researcher is an English language teacher, he only explained the contents of the Informed Consent Form. He asked a staff from the Dean's Office to ask the voluntary participation of the students by signing the Informed Consent Form. It also was explained to the students that they would not be receiving any academic points for participating in the study. Refusal to participate in the study would not affect their class standing as well. Identifiers like names, ages, and sections were removed from the data.

The researcher kept the records for this study confidential in adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012. No information that discloses a respondent's identity was released or published without specific consent to the disclosure. Data was stored in a researcher's laptop with a password so no one can access it. It would be deleted after two years. The consent of the agency was secured before the conduct of this study.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data vis-à-vis the research questions and hypotheses of the study. For a more precise understanding, the research findings are organized in tabular forms followed by narrative discussions.

The Level of Receptive Skills of College Students Before Using Computer-Assisted Language Learning

The first problem in the study aims to assess the baseline proficiency of college students in receptive language skills, before they engage with Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) programs. The analysis provides insights into the students' initial language competency, serving as a foundational reference for evaluating the effectiveness of CALL in the receptive skills of the students. Moreover, receptive skills, encompassing listening and reading, are essential components of language acquisition, facilitating the comprehension of spoken and written language.

Table 1. *Pre-test Scores*

Course	N	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Entrepreneurship	2	0.75	0.35	A1 Basic User
BSBA	6	0.78	0.78	A1 Basic User
MEDTECH	32	1.93	0.69	B1 Independent User
RADTECH	24	1.35	0.95	A2 Basic User
Physical Therapy	17	1.94	0.75	B1 Independent User
Psychology	18	1.93	0.67	B1 Independent User
Pharmacy	20	1.52	0.83	A2 Basic User
Nursing	180	1.51	0.82	A2 Basic User
Pre-Test Scores	299	1.57	0.82	Basic User/ Waystage or Elementary

As presented in Table 1, it can be observed that students pursuing courses with Entrepreneurship and BSBA courses show a mean of 0.75 and 0.78, respectively. The majority of the population only belongs to A1, which refers to basic users for knowledge and understanding of language structure and meaning is at a minimum. On the contrary, Medical Technology (N=32) has a proficiency level of independent users as the population has a mean of 1.93 wherein a sufficient level is achieved for knowledge and understanding of language structure and meaning. For Radiologic Technology students (N=24), a mean of 1.35 was obtained which indicates that they only belong to the proficiency level of A2, a basic user, which means that their proficiency is just a more limited way with knowledge and understanding of language structure and meaning. In a comparable manner, students pursuing degrees in psychology (N=18) and physical therapy (N=17) demonstrate proficiency levels categorized as independent users (B1), with mean scores of 1.93 and 1.94, respectively, demonstrating an acceptable level of linguistic structure and meaning knowledge. Nursing students (N=180) are classified as basic users (A2) with a mean score of 1.51, indicating an average level of knowledge and grasp of language structure and meaning. Pharmacy students (N=20) get a mean score of 1.52, indicating an average user competence level (A2).

Moreover, the pre-test mean score for all participants is 1.57, with a standard deviation of 0.82, and it can be verbally interpreted as Basic User or Elementary. The student's knowledge and comprehension of language structure and meaning are demonstrated below.

These findings explain why different courses had differing levels of language proficiency prior to the invention of computer-assisted language learning. The observed differences in mean scores highlight the range of linguistic abilities among students and serve as a basis for assessing the effectiveness of the language learning intervention.

The Level of Receptive Skills of College Students after using Computer-Assisted Language Learning

The second problem in the study investigates the effectiveness of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) on the receptive

skills of college students. Receptive skills are crucial components of language proficiency. With the integration of technology in language education, particularly through CALL, this research aims to assess the effectiveness of such tools in enhancing students' receptive language abilities. By evaluating the post-implementation levels of college students, this study seeks to contribute valuable insights into the potential benefits and outcomes of incorporating CALL into language learning curricula

Table 2. *Post-Test Scores*

<i>Course</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Entrepreneurship	2	1.10	0.14	A2 Basic User
BSBA	6	1.03	0.08	A2 Basic User
MEDTECH	32	2.29	0.71	B2 Independent User
RADTECH	24	1.71	0.91	B2 Basic User
Physical Therapy	17	2.32	0.60	B2 Independent User
Psychology	18	2.29	0.42	B2 Independent User
Pharmacy	20	1.85	0.75	B1 Basic User
Nursing	180	1.94	0.73	B1 Basic User
Post-Test Scores	299	1.97	0.74	Independent User/ Threshold or Intermediate

The Post-test results provide more information regarding the evaluation of college students' receptive skills utilizing Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) prior to any intervention. The post-test data reveals information on how language proficiency is developing. It consists of participant numbers (N), mean scores, standard deviations (SD), and interpretations.

Notably, the mean score in the area of Entrepreneurship increased from 0.75 to 1.10 (A2 Basic User), showing a below-average comprehension of language structure and meaning. In contrast, BSBA showed an increase from 0.78 to 1.03 (A2 Basic User), indicating a similar degree of proficiency. Also, with an increased mean score of 2.29 (B2 Independent User) after scoring 1.93 on the pre-test, Medical Technology (MEDTECH) demonstrated significant improvement. This indicates a solid understanding of language structure and meaning. Similar increases in mean scores were seen in other courses, including Radiologic Technology (RADTECH), Physical Therapy, Psychology, Pharmacy, and Nursing, indicating an increase toward higher levels of language competency. The post-test results for every course show a steady increasing development, which shows the effectiveness of CALL as an intervention tool for improving college students' receptive skills.

Additionally, the average post-test score for all participants is 1.97, with a standard deviation of 0.74; this result is verbally interpreted as Independent User/Threshold or Intermediate, but it is relatively near the next level. It indicates that students have a good grasp of language meaning and structure. Along with understanding how sentences are put together, students can also use and manipulate language components effectively. This reveals a finding that is similar to Li's (2015) study, which found that using computer-assisted language learning (CALL) exercises significantly improved students' receptive skills. In a comparable manner Wang and Chen's (2018) research showed that CALL-based instruction improved students' receptive skills.

Significant Difference in the Level of Receptive Skills Before and After Using Computer-Assisted Language Learning?

The third problem in the study investigates the significant differences in the level of receptive language skills before and after the implementation of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL). By conducting a comparative analysis, this research aims to shed light on the effectiveness of CALL in fostering positive changes in receptive language proficiency.

Table 3. *Significant Difference in the Level of Receptive Skills Before and After Using Computer-Assisted Language Learning*

<i>Statistic</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>P</i>
-12.49	295.00	<.0001

Table 3 shows the significant difference in the level of receptive skills before and after using Computer-Assisted Language Learning. Since the p-value ($t=12.49$, $p < 0.0001$) is less than 0.05, then it rejects the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the level of receptive skills using CALL before and after the intervention. Likewise, it is suggested that using CALL enhances students' proficiency in receptive skills. Warschauer and Healey (1998), who conducted a study comparing the efficacy of a regular language classroom with a CALL setting, also supported this finding. They discovered that students in the CALL setting interacted and engaged with the language at higher levels, which aided in their capacity to create their own knowledge and comprehension of the language.

Conclusion

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) in enhancing the receptive skills of college students. Moreover, through a comparative analysis, the study seeks to provide insights into the potential

benefits of integrating CALL strategy into language learning environments to improved receptive skills development among students.

For the research question number 1, the level of receptive skills of the students before the intervention is Basic User or Elementary which means that the student exhibits below knowledge and understanding of language structure and meaning.

For the research question number 2, the level of the receptive skills of the students after the intervention is Independent User/ Threshold or Intermediate which means that the student exhibits acceptable knowledge and understanding of language structure and meaning.

For the research question number 3, the result also shows that there is a significant difference in the level of receptive skills using CALL before and after the intervention. This also proved that the study by Sánchez-López, Munuera-Soler, and Dominguez-Garrido (2021) on the effects of CALL on receptive skills of college students revealed that CALL had a significant positive effect on both listening and reading skills. The level of receptive skills of college students before and after the intervention became higher which implies that the use of the said intervention could be effective and helpful in the improvement of the said skills.

Based on the results of the findings of the study and conclusion, the following suggestions were made:

For Curriculum Planners and School Administrators, the findings of the study shows that CALL is a useful tool in improving the level of receptive skills of the learners. It is therefore recommended to use this tool in teaching the English language.

For English Teachers, it is recommended that they may include CALL in their classes. Aside from the fact that it is fun and easy to use, students significantly learn the fun way as well.

For the Students, the findings may provide their feedback as to their level of receptive skills. It is recommended that they may continue to use CALL in their learning process.

For Future Researchers, it is recommended that they also explore investigating the effectiveness of other Computer-Assisted Language Learning tools. They may also study other communication skills.

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